

NAME AREA NAME SURNAME STATION 000

SITE ID INVESTIGATOR

DATE YYYY MM DD Sea state 00

Precipitation Clouds coverage Day / Night

SAMPLING

CAST 000

NET Model : MystiNet CLASSIC HSN DIODON Tow type : HORIZONTAL VERTICAL

Other NAME Mesh size : 20 µm 50 µm OTHER 000 µm

Deployment parameters :

ROPE ANGLE 000 ° (Angle vs vertical) DEPTH MIN 000 m DEPTH MAX 000 m ROPE OUT 000 m (in water)

START

LAT N/S DD° MM.MMM' LONG E/W DD° MM.MMM' UTC TIME HH MM

END

LAT N/S DD° MM.MMM' LONG E/W DD° MM.MMM' UTC TIME HH MM

COMMENTS

ADDITIONAL INFOS

NET TOW SPEED 000 knots

AIR T° 000 °C SEA WATER T° °C WIND SPEED knots WIND DIRECTION ° WAVE DIRECTION °

CTD Model NAME ROPE OUT 000 m

FLOWMETER Model NAME START 00000 END

SECCHI DISC DISAPPEARING POINT 00 m AGAIN SIGHTED 00 m

COMMENTS

FILTRATION TREATMENT

FINAL VOLUME AFTER NET RINSING : mL

FILTER n°1

Porosity : μm

BARCODE

START TIME UTC

END TIME UTC

TUBE ID

FILTERED VOLUME mL Saturation : YES NO

FILTER n°2

Porosity : μm

BARCODE

START TIME UTC

END TIME UTC

TUBE ID

FILTERED VOLUME mL Saturation : YES NO

COMMENTS

IMAGING TREATMENT

FINAL VOLUME AFTER NET RINSING : mL

FIRST

PROJECT NAME

STATION ID

DILUTION

Acq ID ti import

Nb of images

Nb of Objects

SECOND

PROJECT NAME

STATION ID

DILUTION

Acq ID ti import

Nb of images

Nb of Objects

COMMENTS